

Historically tracing the shifting courses of the Ganges and resultant river-bank erosion in Malda: Analyzing its impact on the life of the people

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Abstract: The district of Malda faced various changes in the course of the Ganges from 12th Century onwards, that continued till the second half of the 20th Century and later also. The shifting courses of the Ganges in this region led to the river-bank erosion in course of time which impacted the life of the people living in the adjacent area hugely. Due to this phenomenon, from ancient period to the modern era, the population are seen to be displaced. This persistent river-bank erosion has challenged the life and livelihood of the people largely, thus threatening the sustainable development. In all aspects, the life of the people has been endangered in this way that has shown no sign to be checked till date.

Keywords: Shifting, river-bank erosion, Displacement, persistent, sustainability, endangering.

Introduction

Environment and the mankind are related to each other. Therefore, any kind of environmental hazard leaves various consequences on the human civilization. Amongst these environmental hazards, riverbank erosion is a major aspect of discussion for its direct interaction with physical and socio-cultural environment. In Malda district of West Bengal, particularly in its Diara region, the Ganges-river changed its courses at various point of time in the past decades, which later led to the river-bank erosion. In course of time this bank-erosion took much more dangerous form that resulted in huge difficulties for the concerned people. By devastating the riverine regions this environmental hazard exterminated the people from their root and affected their life and livelihood severely.

1. Historically tracing the shifting courses of the Ganges: From 12th -20th Century:

In mid-12th century, Ganga used to flow along the channel below Englishbazar (now Mahananda flows there). When Ganga started showing tendency to shift westward, the Sena ruler Lakshansena shifted the capital southward from Lakshmanawati to Nuddeeyah. Later also, with the river remaining unstable over a long period, Alauddin Ali Shah shifted his capital to Pandua in 1342. The capital was again shifted to Gaur in the mid- 15th Century during the reign of Nasiruddin Mahmud Shah. However, following the conquest of Gaur by Sher Shah afterwards, the status of this major medieval city began to decline clearly, as the consequence of renewed river migration. When Rannell visited the region two centuries later in 1776, he found the Ganges flowing more than 16 km to the city's west¹.

This shows the drastic changes in the river-course over time. The 17th and 18th centuries were the period of great changes so far as the course of the Ganga is concerned. Bhagirathi through which water of the Ganges used to pass from 12th to 16th century, was no longer the main stream of the river as it lost its connection with Ganges except only during the Rains. Padma channel became a broad stream in 17th - 18th century, carrying the bulk of the Ganges's water.² The famous sur-

veyor Buchanon Hamilton showed, in 1810, the general set of the river was away from the plains of Malda and Rajmahal was on the riverbank. while later in 1870, due to the eastward migration of the Ganges, Rajmahal, became deserted. It was caused by the river which after rounding the Rajmahal hills, came against the island char of Bhutni Diara and followed the eastern channel instead of the western. In the late 19th Century due to this eastward migration of the Ganges, considerable erosion occurred on the left-bank i.e Malda bank. This affected the Manikchak and Kaliachak-2 blocks³. The Diara is a fertile, low-lying region, which stretching over the ancient floodplain comprises a sandbank-base overlaid by colloidal silts. These are vulnerable to saturation. The river by increasing its flow, strikes the layer, the base is scrubbed, and causes bank failure.

De Barro and Gastaldi Provided the oldest of modern maps of Ganges delta. In the second decade of the 20th century, the course of the Ganges between Rajmahal and Farakka was straight and aligned in a south-easterly direction. This course is described in the topographical sheet bearing No.72 P/13 (1:63360), surveyed in the year 1922-23. This is very much important to mention here that - this is a changed course of the river as previously Ganges flowed along an altogether different course dashing Gour (Gaur), as reflected in the writings of R.K. Mukherjee⁴ and Sir J.N.Sarkar.⁵

However, there was an important event-the construction of the Farakka Barrage which was commissioned in 1975. According to various scholars and intellectuals, this Barrage contributed largely to the increased rate of the Ganges-bank erosion in Malda. By creating an obstruction in the usual flow of the river, this has reduced the water-velocity which resulted in sedimentation in the river-bed. This resulted in the changing river-course. Sedimentation upstream of the Barrage, coupled with natural swing of Ganga made the river swing to the left. It resulted in encroaching the left bank of the Ganges leading to erosion in thousands of villages, downstream of the Barrage causing floods. The Irrigation Department of West Bengal (Report for 1997-2001) has agreed not only about the erosion having caused by the Farakka Barrage, but also cautioned about the possibility of out-flanking of the Farakka Barrage itself. The river being interrupted, tried to find the way to flow through the side-banks. As the river-bank on the Malda side i.e the left bank is much more softer due to its geological structure than the Jharkhand side (consisted of igneous rock), huge erosion occurred in Malda.

2. Impact of the Ganges-bank erosion on the life of the people in Malda-Land-loss and various sufferings of the people:

Between 1931-1978 the amount of lost land was 14,335 hectare⁶ and 1979-2005, the amount of land loss was 19,685 hectare due to Ganges-erosion in Malda. According to the report of the Irrigation and Waterways Department of Government of West Bengal, from 1931- 2005, total 34,019 hectares land got eroded in Malda.

In Malda, on the left bank of Ganga for a long time five community development blocks have been more or less affected by erosion from around 1965-1970. They are Manikchak, Kaliachak 1, Kaliachak 2, Kaliachak 3 and Ratua. According to the report of the Committee set up by Planning Commission- nearly 4.5 lakhs of people have lost their homes due to left bank erosion and 22 mouzas have gone in the river of Manickchak, Kaliachak 1 and Kaliachak 2. The following information is derived from the 1991 Census Handbook of Malda. In this book certain villages are indicated as uninhabited which had actually been washed away by river-bank

erosion.⁷

The people, being affected by the river-bank erosion, went through several difficulties in life. Firstly, losing their land and home they were displaced to other places- sometimes to the high-roads of the city making temporary shelters, sometimes to any nearby villages. In search of livelihood often they had to migrate to other states also, out of West Bengal. Often they shifted to the river-islands or char-lands in order to take refuge. These erosion-affected families were mainly agricultural who had to shift to other works. Majority of them worked as labourers in various small or large factories in the outside states as wage-labours. Some had to work as fishermen or boatmen in the villages where they migrated to. Needless to say, their earnings from these spheres were not enough or much lower than what they used to earn through farming in their own lands. The marginal cultivators, who had been reduced to landlessness now swelled the ranks of agricultural labourers, and they kept increasing in number in the Diara tract (Malda Diara include Englishbazar, Manikchak, Kaliachak I, II, III). Others shifted to trade or artisanship. Many getting reduced to landlessness, struggled to live. Some were belonging to combined category of both marginal cultivators with wage labour, in order to survive. With limited livelihood opportunities, these people kept struggling with poverty.

They used to live in altogether a different kind of world. With no basic facilities available in those remote char-lands, condition of health system and infrastructure was also very poor. The life of people were in complete uncertainty and danger. Any person suffering from any disease, especially serious diseases did not get any proper treatment due to lack of hospitals or even primary health centres, even without any doctor or medical stuffs in and around. Therefore, high rate of death of pregnant women or elders were often observed here. It took several hours to reach town or any better place where proper treatment was available for patients. This too was possible by means of boat or other forms of difficult and tiresome transportations.

Access to safe drinking water was another problem faced by these ill-fated people. As Diara region was arsenic-prone, arsenic fluoride contamination was a serious problem here. Due to this, liver, heart and kidney related diseases were found among them. Thus without food, treatment and even clean drinking water they continued to survive like creatures and this situation have been continued over years. Security of women was also an important issue in these remote areas. The children having no scope of going to school remained uneducated day after day. This increased the rate of various illegal associations amongst them especially in their teen-age. All these circumstances made the erosion-affected population very much vulnerable to any further river-bank erosion. However, the tragedy is that this problem is not to be stopped and would happen further in a cyclic process, thus devastating their life again and again.

3.Field Survey; Result and Discussion:

The field survey of this study took place in Birnagar of Kaliachak-III block of Malda district. Out of total 50 families who were interviewed there, each family had different categories of earning members. The difference was noticed mainly on the basis of the places where they migrated to. Their nature of work also varied.

A pie chart is given below, figured out of the information and statistics as have come out from the field survey, occurred in the particular area. The survey has made the scenario of the life the people, affected by the Ganges-bank erosion,

much more clear. These families were selected on the basis of simple random sampling, from the particular area where the survey was conducted.

From the pie chart given above it is reflected that out of the total earning male members of the surveyed households, 70% migrated to the states outside West Bengal-such as Gujrat, Kerala, Maharastra (Mumbai mainly), Delhi etc. Their family members often remained in the nearby villages or the river-islands. Out of the rest 20% migrated to the nearby city areas- mainly the embankments or highroads. The remaining 10% have been living in the river-islands.

These displaced population belonged to farming communities. But due to the river-bank erosion, under the changed circumstances, they adapted new works. These new works were not of course very much easy for them to learn, still they had to adjust with this transformation of their life. A table is given below to understand the work-scenario of these people.

Type of the displaced people	Their new work
People who moved to the different states outside West Bengal	As labors in various small/medium/large factories or industries
People who moved to nearby city or villages (embankments or highroads)	Small shops, small business
People who moved to the river-island areas	Boating, fishing or nothing at all

People who went through the experience of migrating to various states/places, have now been old-aged, thus returned to the areas where the survey was conducted. Along with them, those people who have been migrated to those new places-whether different states outside or others, have also been going through the same kind of experiences. All of these are described into three categories in the table given above- those who moved to the different states out of West Bengal, mainly worked there as wage-labors in various kind of industrial factories or construction work of buildings. Those who moved to nearby city areas, generally engaged themselves in small business-shops. They mainly lived in the embankment areas

on the highway side making temporary shelters. The people who moved to the river-island areas and did not further try for any other work outside, passed their days by fishing or boating or sometime having no work to do at all to earn their bread. Needless to say this condition led themselves into extreme poverty.

Maximum of these households has at least one member in each family (sometimes 2 members) who migrated out of West Bengal. This shows how the Ganges river-bank erosion over years has harmed the life of the population by grasping the lands in huge amount. In search of shelter and livelihood, maximum of those households had started being displaced from their original homeland long before -around 1960-1965. Therefore, they have migrated at least 3-4 times. Despite lot of struggles, these ill-fated people have been offered from life nothing but sheer helplessness.

They did not get the basic civic amenities, not even proper ration or any essential commodities. Moreover, in the families where the earning male member has migrated to the outside states, rest of the members has gone through a very difficult situation. Sometimes, finding the earning of the migrated male members not enough, the female members had to bind Bidi- in order to run the household. This was an added responsibility for the women who besides taking care of the children and old-aged members of the family, also had to share the financial responsibilities for their family. Despite of struggling very hard, these people could not see any ray of hopes which could uplift their living condition. In the absence of a minimum structure of a civilization, they practically have been living a life - completely isolated from the mainstream of the society. The loss of land, home, assets made them suffer through an identity crisis also. Their emotional sufferings as have been continued year after year, is unbearable. The life they live or have been living, is full of only misery and deprivation.

Conclusion

The people living in the river-adjacent areas are very much attached to the river emotionally. Despite the erosion year after year and their consequent sufferings, they cannot find any other way to live, going away from the river. As a result, they are put in the cycle of 'river-bank erosion-displacement-river-bank erosion-displacement'- the repetition of the same cycle. In this way, they go through huge helplessness and difficulties. In Malda, as have been seen through this study, the people having lost everything to the river, went through huge sufferings. Apart from huge loss in land, home, assets- the identity crisis of these people shows how helpless is the mankind in front of the nature. It is very much unfortunate that we live in a civilization, of which the existence of these people is also a part. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the larger part of the society to bring these people back to the mainstream of life which they also deserve. In order to do that, improving the situation of river-bank erosion by river-basin management as well as addressing the rehabilitation issue of the displaced people- is an utmost need. In this respect, with the help of various river-experts and eminent personalities from various concerned fields, some positivity can definitely be hoped for.

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